

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF *BALATISARA* (CHILDHOOD DIARRHOEA): ILLNESS OR SYMPTOM

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ABSTRACT

Children, particularly those under the age of twelve, frequently suffer from diarrhoea. Approximately 5,25,000 children die from diarrheal illness each year, making it the second most common cause of death for children under five (WHO May 2017). The majority of diarrheal illnesses in children are not caused by bacteria. *Ayurveda* plays a significant part in the natural treatment of illness by balancing the body's constituents (*Dosha, Dhatu, and Mala*). In addition to certain particular effects of the plant itself (*Prabhava*), herbs have constitutional effects based on their taste (*Rasa*), potency (*Virya*), and post-digestive impact (*Vipaka*). We can protect kids from the negative effects of antibiotics by utilizing medicinal herbs as medication.

KEYWORDS: *Balatisara*, antibiotics, childhood diarrhoea.

INTRODUCTION

With an estimated 1.5 million fatalities annually, diarrheal illnesses are the second most prevalent cause of child death worldwide, accounting for a significant part of children deaths—roughly 18%.^[1] UNICEF reports that only five nations—India, Nigeria, Afghanistan, Pakistan, and Ethiopia—account for more than half of all fatalities. According to WHO and UNICEF estimates, children under the age of five in underdeveloped nations experience almost 2.5 billion bouts of diarrhoea each year.^[2] It was the second leading cause of mortality

for children under five in 2012. Another significant contributing factor to infant malnutrition is diarrhea.^[3] In addition to having an impact on children's health, it is thought to be the cause of infant mortality, particularly in tropical and subtropical nations. According to WHO estimates, rotavirus infection kills between 90,000 and 1,53,000 children in India annually.

The majority of diarrheal illnesses in children are not caused by bacteria. Antibiotic usage is still only advised for invasive bacterial gastrointestinal tract infections. The majority of paediatric diarrheal illnesses involve the unethical use of antibiotics. Antibiotics exacerbate viral diarrhoea, and the youngster may become extremely dehydrated. It is crucial to note that regular antibiotic usage not only endangers a child's healthy gut flora but also leads to drug resistance in the underlying infection.

In our clinical experience, we have discovered that Ayurvedic medications are quite useful for episodes of diarrhoea. However, this needs to be demonstrated using research standards. Numerous anti-diarrheal medications that provide better support and more sophisticated treatment approaches are available in traditional medical systems (*Ayurveda*). *Ayurveda* employs the natural herbs' innate capacity to treat digestive issues and enhance the body's metabolism. In this case, *Ayurveda* is crucial since it balances the body's constituents (*Dosha*, *Dhatu*, and *Mala*) in a natural way to treat illness. In addition to certain particular effects of the plant itself (*Prabhava*), herbs have constitutional effects based on their taste (*Rasa*), potency (*Virya*), and post-digestive impact (*Vipaka*). We can protect kids from the negative effects of antibiotics by utilizing medicinal herbs as medication.

DIARRHOEA

Frequent passage of watery faeces, a rise in stool frequency due to more bowel movements compared to each person's normal habit, or an increase in stool frequency and fluidity so that stool takes on the shape of a container. Another definition of diarrhoea is a change in a typical bowel movement that is marked by an increase in the volume, frequency, or water content of stool. The WHO's definition of diarrhea.^[4]

Three or more loose or watery stools or more frequent passages than are typical for that person are considered diarrhoea (stool consistency is more essential than frequency). The WHO states that the following conditions are not considered diarrhoea: frequent passage of formed stools; loose, "pasty" stools passed by breastfed babies; stool passed during or right after feeding as a result of the gastrocolic reflex; irritable bowel syndrome; and frequently

loose greenish yellow stools on the third and fourth days of life, referred to as transition stools.

Causes of diarrhea^[5]: Some causative factors of diarrhoea are-

Parasites and worms, lactose intolerance brought on by a lack of the enzyme lactase, which is necessary for breaking down lactose, diarrhoea, intestinal illnesses and bowel disorders (viral and bacterial infections), allergies to specific foods, side effects from antibiotics and other medications, unsanitary conditions like overcrowding, a lack of clean drinking water, and a trend toward bottle feeding instead of breastfeeding.

ATISARA (DIARRHOEA)

According to *Dalhana's* commentary on the *Sushruta Samhita*, one of the hallmarks of *atisara* is the increased production of watery stool. In *Madhukosh Vyakhya* on *Madhav Nidaan*, *Vijayrakshita* described *atisara* as excessive liquid passing via the anus.

BALATISARA (CHILDHOOD DIARRHOEA)

The *Harita Samhita* is where the term "*Balatisara*" first appears in relation to therapy.^[6] Although it has not been identified as a distinct entity in *Brihatrayi*, the name "*balatisara*" literally refers to *atisara* that occurs in children.

However, there are a few sporadic references to the term "*balatisara*" in relation to the treatment of *atisara* in children in *Lahutrasi*.

Ayurvedic literature has addressed *atisara* (diarrhoea) in great depth, but not specifically with regard to children. Ayurveda does not provide a thorough explanation of *Atisara* in youngsters. However, Ayurvedic literature has highlighted a particular illness called *Kaumarabhryta* where diarrhoea is a key symptom. Many ailments, including *dantoddbhedjanyatisara*, *ksheeralasaka*, *vyadhij phakka*, *revati*, *putna*, etc., are said to cause *atisara*. Scriptures do not specifically describe *Balatisara* as a sickness, but they do provide therapeutic options specifically for *Balatisara* (diarrhea in children). Adults and children may have the same *samprapti* of *atisara*, but they differ in terms of additional etiological elements (such as *dantodbheda*, *balagrahas*, *ksheeralasaka*, etc.) and higher morbidity and death. According to *Acharya Charaka and Sushruta*, "*krimi*" is a crucial component of the *atisara* in children. Only the infancy stage is affected by these additional etiological elements that distinguish *balatisara* from *atisara*. Examples of diarrhoea that exclusively happens during

infancy include dental diarrhoea, lactose intolerance diarrhoea, rotavirus diarrhoea, etc. *Samprapti* for the remaining *atisara* that occurs during childhood is the same for adults and children.

Nidana (Causes of Diarrhoea)

Common *nidana* for all kinds of *atisaar* was stated by *Acharya Sushruta*.^[7] consumption of foods such as *guru*, *atisnigdha*, *atiruksha*, *atiushna*, *atidravya*, and *atisheeta*. consumption of foods that are incompatible. eating in *adhyashna*, *vishmashana*, and *ajirna*. Consuming too much water or drinking tainted water. Drinking too much alcohol, suppressing one's natural desires, and experiencing "*krimi*." overuse or improper application of *Panchkarma*. psychological aspects, such as an urge of shock or dread. consumption of food without considering the season, *Graha* (Infections).

Samprapti Chakra^[8]

Samprapti Ghataka

Dosha – Vata pradhana tridosha

Dushya – Rasa, rakta, mansa, meda, mutra, purisha

Adhishthana- mahastrotasa

Srotasa- Annavaha, purishavaha, udakvaha

Strotodushti- Atipravriti, vimarga gamana

Etiopathogenesis of Atisara based on Samanya Samprapti

We may comprehend that *asatmya aahara vihara* creates *mandagni*, which results in *dhatvagnimandta*, after analysing *samanyasamprapti* of *atisara* according to many *Acharyas*. *Mandadhavagni* causes a rise in *jaliyagundharmisharirikdhatumootra*, *sweda*, etc. When *jatharaagni* and *dhatvagni* are in a normal state, they often develop. In the *mandagni* condition, the formation of *mootra*, *sweda*, etc. is disrupted, and excessive fluid secretion into the intestinal lumen follows. This excess water content (*jaleeyansh*) is carried down into the big intestine (*pakwashay*) by vitiated *vata*, where it mixes with faeces and creates *atisara*, or the downward flow of watery stool.

The examination of *samanyasamprapti* above revealed three key elements that contribute to the pathophysiology of *atisara*: *mandagni (tryodashvidhaagni)*, *jaliyanshprachurta*, and *vatavikriti*.

Types of Atisara

Acharya Sushruta^[9] states that there are about six different kinds of *atisara*: *Vataja*, *Pitajja*, *Kaphaja*, *Sannipataja*, *Shokaja*, and *Amajaatisara*. *Vataja atisara* includes *Bhayaja atisara* as given by *Acharya Charaka* and *Vagbhata*^[10] instead of *Amaja atisara*. *Pitajja atisara* includes *Rakta atisara*. *Amaja atisara* is part of *Sannipataja atisara*, according to *Acharya Charaka*.

Madhav nidana^[11] mentioned 7 types of *atisara*, 6 types told by *Acharya Sushruta* and one *raktaja*. *Acharya Sharangdhar*^[12] also mentioned 7 types of *atisara*, 6 types told by *Acharya Sushruta* and one *bhayaja*. *Acharya bhaishajyaratnavali*^[13] mentioned 8 types of *atisara*, 7 types told by *Acharya Sharangdhar* and one *jwaraja*. *Harita Samhita*^[14] mentioned only one type as *jwara atisara*. *Acharya Charaka*^[15] mentioned 36 types of *atisara in sidhithana*.

Poorvaroop (prodromal symptoms)

Gatraavasada (general malaise), *Vitsanga* (constipation), *Anilsannirodha* (non-elimination of *vata*), *Adhman* (abdominal distension), *Avipaka* (indigestion), and prickling sensations in *Hridaya*, *Nabhi*, *Payu*, *Udar*, and *Kukshi Pradesh*.^[16]

Roop (Symptoms)

Discoloration of body, Uneasiness in mouth, Fatigue, Insomnia, Absence of functions of *Vaayu* (flatus).^[17]

***Vishista lakshana* (sign and symptoms)**

The signs and symptoms listed in *Madhav Nidana*^[18]

Vataja atisara: Blackish, frothy, rough, Ama, and tiny amounts of faeces passed, together with stomach ache.

Pittaja atisara: Frequent burning sensations, thirst, sweating, fainting, and passing of yellowish, greenish, blackish, and foul-smelling feces.

Kaphaja atisara: Passing unctuous, white, slimy, thick, foul-smelling poo with mucus is known as *kaphaja atisara*.

Sannipataja atisara: The passage of faeces with or without discomfort, which might be yellow, green, blue, or reddish in color and have a fatty texture. This variety of *atisara* is difficult to treat and exhibits symptoms of all three categories.

Shokaja atisara: According to *Acharya Charaka*^[19] and *Vagbhata*, its signs and symptoms are similar to *Vataja atisara*.

Aamaja atisara: Passing of stool frequently of various colors, abdominal pain are the main features of *amajaatisara*.^[20]

***Mala pariksha* (Examination of Stool)^[21]**

Pariksha mainly include *srotopariksha* and *malapariksha*.

Srotopariksha: *Pureeshavahasrotas* is the predominant *Strotas* involved in *atisara*. *Krichrenaalpalpam*, *sasabda*, *sashoolam*, *athidravam*, *atigrathitham*, and *atibahu* are its *dushti* symptoms.

Malapareeksha: It helps distinguish between *ama mala* and *pakwa mala* and is essential for identifying aberrant components in stool, such as *ama*, *rakta*, *kapha*, *krimi*, *puya*, etc. *Acharya Chakradutta* and *Ashtanga Sangraha* state that faeces is in *ama awastha* if it sinks in water and *nirama* if it floats, with the exception of situations including excess fluidity, compactness, coldness, and the presence of mucus. The ama stool has an unpleasant odour,

severe flatulence, uncomfortable constipation, and unusual salivation. These related symptoms won't affect *nirama mala*.

Ayurvedic Perspective of Dehydration

According to Ayurveda, severe *pipasa lakshana*, which is referenced in the Kashyap Samhita, is associated with symptoms of dehydration. These include: palate, lips, tongue, and throat dryness; inability to detect with the eyes and hearing; drowsiness; altered sensorium and orientation; lack of appetite; overall weakness; and tongue protrusion.^[22]

TREATMENT

Atisara receives the same basic care as adults. It is important to first determine if the stool is *saam or nirama*. *Langhana* is recommended if the stool is in Saam state. However, excessive *langhana* treatment is not recommended. Bowel-binding treatments, or *Sangrahana* therapy, should be used if stool is *nirama*. Constipative medications must not be used to halt it. *Haritaki* is used as a moderate laxative if the diarrhoea is accompanied by gripping pain (difficulty voiding). *Pramathya with Deepan and Pachana* characteristics should be administered if the doshas are significantly inflamed.^[23]

Amapachan is the primary line of treatment for *amatisar*, whereas *stambhan* is the first line of treatment for *pakwatisar*. Due to their fragile nature and underdeveloped tissues (*dhatu*), children cannot benefit from the use of traditional *amapachan* therapy, such as *langhan*, or the usage of medications with *katu, ushna, or tikshna* qualities. In youngsters, the illness rapidly worsens. Thus, we are eager to see how long it will take from *Amavastha to Niramavastha*. In the current situation, there is a need for an ayurvedic formulation that can help children with both acute and chronic types of diarrhea, or *amavastha and pakkvavastha*. These formulas are specifically referenced for infantile diarrhea (*balatisara*) in Ayurvedic classics such as *Sharangdhar, Yogratnakar, Vangsen, and Chakradatta*.

Pathyapathya (Do's and Don'ts)

Pathya: Fruits, cereals, hot water are considered as pathya. According to *Yogaratanakara*, sleep, *langhana*, goat milk, cow milk, ghee, butter extracted from goat or cow milk, curd, buttermilk are considered as *pathya*. Diet should be restricted to light food like soup of *Mudga siddha with Shunthi, kanji, yavagu, tarpana*, etc.

Apathya: In *Kashyapa Samhita*, intake of garlic, unctuous substance, meat soup and sudation are considered as *apthya*. According to *Yogaratanakara*, waking during night, heavy foods and drink are considered as *apathya*.

DISCUSSION

The following factors emerged from the discussion above as being responsible for the pathophysiology of *atisara*: *Jaliyanshprachurta*, *Vatavikriti*, and *Mandagni* (*tryodashvidhaagni*). Therefore, we require a mix of substances that address every pathogenic aspect of *atisara* in kids. *Amapachan* is the primary line of treatment for *amatisar*, whereas *stambhan* is the first line of treatment for *pakwatisar*. Due to their sensitive nature, children cannot benefit from the use of traditional *amapachan* therapy, such as *langhan*, or the use of medications with *katu*, *ushna*, or *tikshna* qualities. *Aacharya Charak* stated that drugs with characteristics like *katu*, *tikshna*, and *ushna* should not be used on youngsters when outlining the common treatment philosophy. Children's frail bodies and underdeveloped tissues also contribute to the disease's rapid progression. Thus, we are eager to see how long it will take from *Amavastha* to *Niramavastha*. In the current situation, a formulation that can help with both *amavastha* and *pakvavastha* phases of diarrhoea is required. Such formulas are addressed specifically for infantile diarrhoea (*balatisara*) in Ayurvedic classics such as *Sharangdhar*, *Yogratnakar*, *Vangsen*, and *Chakradatta*.

CONCLUSION

After analysing a large body of literature, we have concluded that *Atisara* is characterized as a symptom of several disorders, including *dantoddbhedjanyatisara*, *ksheeralasaka*, *vyadhij phakka*, *revati*, *putna*, etc. *balaagraha*. Scriptures do not specifically describe *Balatisara* as an illness, but they do provide particular treatments for treating *Balatisara* (diarrhea in children). No acharya has advised treating children in accordance with *amatisara* or *pakwatisara* or adhering to *langhan*. Not based on dosha dominance or phases of *balaatisara*, our acharyas have also offered a single treatment for *balatisara* in classics. The aforementioned study makes it clear that a combination of substances with the qualities of *deepan*, *pachan*, *grahi*, and *stambhan* would be helpful for treating diarrhoea in children.

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